

New Non-Lattice Optimal Kissing Configurations in \mathbb{R}^6 and \mathbb{R}^7 via Gyration

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Abstract

We introduce *gyration*, a modification of Cohn and Rajagopal's layer replacement [4], which reflects one hemisphere of a spherical code through its axis rather than through the equatorial hyperplane. We describe how to enumerate all valid gyration axes and apply this to contact polytopes in dimensions 3–9.

Most significantly, $\Gamma_6 \triangleq G(1_{22})$ and $\Gamma_7 \triangleq G(2_{31})$ are **new optimal kissing configurations** in \mathbb{R}^6 and \mathbb{R}^7 : non-isometric to the E_6 and E_7 root polytopes, each with seven distinct inner products and 2 vertex orbits. Γ_6 has 72 points and automorphism group of order 3 840; Γ_7 has 126 points and $|\text{Aut}| = 103\,680$.

In dimension 8, repeated gyration of D_8 about multiple axes produces thousands of Gram-inequivalent 112-point codes on S^7 , including a unique vertex-transitive configuration, χ_8 , which is antipodal-free, has only three distinct inner products, and $|\text{Aut}| = 224$. It is a hybrid of 56 roots of D_8 and 56 roots of $E_8 \setminus D_8$.

We analyze the Gram spectra, automorphism groups, and rigidity of these codes.

1 Introduction

Determining the kissing number $k(n)$, the maximum number of non-overlapping unit spheres that can touch a central sphere, is a central problem in discrete geometry. While exact values are known only for $n \leq 4$ and $n \in \{8, 24\}$, finding configurations that achieve or improve upon known bounds remains a primary objective. For decades, the only known configurations achieving the conjectured $k(5) = 40$ and $k(6) = 72$ were lattice-based, arising from the D_5 and E_6 root systems.

Recent discoveries have challenged this assumption. In dimension 5, Szöllősi [13] discovered a third optimal configuration Q_5 via computer search. Cohn and Rajagopal [4] subsequently characterized Q_5 as a *layer replacement* within the D_5 root system: they partition the D_5 vertices into layers by a hyperplane, discard one layer, and replace it with the reflection of the opposite layer through that hyperplane.

In this paper we introduce *gyration*, a modification of layer replacement, which reflects one hemisphere through its *axis* rather than through the equatorial hyperplane.

First, gyration is an involution: applying it twice with the same axis recovers the original code. Because it transforms each vertex in place rather than discarding a hemisphere, the output is again a valid spherical code and can itself be gyrated about a different axis. Moreover, non-trivial gyration of a centrally symmetric code always breaks central symmetry (Proposition 3). In dimension 8, iterated gyration starting from D_8 yields thousands of Gram-inequivalent 112-point kissing configurations on S^7 , including a vertex-transitive code χ_8 with only three distinct inner products.

Second, gyration applies to codes that are *not* centrally symmetric, where it genuinely differs from layer replacement.

Third, the null-space enumeration of gyration axes (Proposition 4) provides a systematic search framework that identifies *all* gyrations of a given code, revealing multi-axis configurations and negative results alike.

We write $\Gamma_n = G(E_n)$ for the gyration of the E_n root system. The most striking results are $\Gamma_6 = G(1_{22})$ and $\Gamma_7 = G(2_{31})$, **new optimal kissing configurations** in \mathbb{R}^6 and \mathbb{R}^7 respectively. Γ_6 is a 72-point configuration achieving the conjectured $k(6) = 72$, non-isometric to the E_6 root system, with seven distinct inner products and automorphism group of order 3840. Γ_7 is a 126-point configuration achieving the conjectured $k(7) = 126$, non-isometric to the E_7 root system, also with seven distinct inner products and $|\text{Aut}| = 103\,680$. These are the first analytically constructed and structurally characterized non-lattice optimal arrangements in their respective dimensions. (Numerically discovered non-lattice optimal configurations in \mathbb{R}^6 were previously obtained by Andreev and Kallus [2].)

We also show that the higher-dimensional gyrated codes ($n = 5$ through 8) are infinitesimally rigid, in contrast to the flexible anticuboctahedron in \mathbb{R}^3 .

Summary of contributions.

1. Introduction and analysis of the *gyration* operator, an involution on spherical codes that generalises layer replacement.
2. A complete enumeration of all gyration axes for any code (Proposition 4).
3. A practical heuristic search algorithm that discovers gyration axes without exhaustive null-space enumeration.
4. A collection of novel kissing configurations, including the Q_n family ($n = 5, 6, 7, 8$).
5. The new optimal codes Γ_6 and Γ_7 .
6. An enormous number of Gram-inequivalent 112-point codes in \mathbb{R}^8 .
7. The vertex-transitive code χ_8 .
8. Analytical constructions for all of the above codes.

Computational verification. All inner product spectra and Gram equivalences reported in this paper are established analytically. Automorphism group orders, facet counts, and rigidity dimensions have been verified numerically using NumPy [12].

2 The gyration operator

Given a spherical code and a choice of axis, the gyration operator partitions the vertices into two hemispheres and reflects the “upper” hemisphere *through* the axis while leaving the remaining vertices unchanged. Since gyration is a bijection—the reflection ρ is invertible and acts only on \mathcal{V}^+ , while the remaining vertices are unchanged—it always preserves the number of vertices.

Construction 1 (Gyration). Let $C \subset S^{n-1}$ be a spherical code and $\hat{a} \in S^{n-1}$ a unit vector (the *axis*). Partition $C = \mathcal{V}^+ \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \mathcal{V}^-$ according to the sign of $\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle$. Define the reflection through \hat{a} :

$$\rho(v) = 2\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle \hat{a} - v.$$

Figure 1: Gyration of the cuboctahedron.

The *gyration* of C about \hat{a} is

$$G_{\hat{a}}(C) = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \rho(\mathcal{V}^+).$$

The gyration replaces \mathcal{V}^+ with $\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$ while keeping $\mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0$ unchanged. When the axis is clear from context, we write simply $G(C)$.

Geometrically, ρ preserves the component of each vertex along \hat{a} and negates the component perpendicular to it.

The name “gyration” is drawn from the classical *gyrobicupola*, the anticuboctahedron (J_{27}), which is obtained from the cuboctahedron by rotating one cupola through 60° about the axis joining the centres of the two opposite triangular faces. This rotation is equivalent to reflecting the cupola through the same axis, a formulation that generalizes more readily to higher dimensions.

The gyration operation is an *involution*: applying it twice with the same axis recovers the original code. For example, gyrating the anticuboctahedron recovers the cuboctahedron.

Proposition 2 (Involution). *For any spherical code C and any unit axis \hat{a} ,*

$$G_{\hat{a}}(G_{\hat{a}}(C)) = C.$$

Proof. Write $G_{\hat{a}}(C) = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$. Since ρ preserves inner products with \hat{a} :

$$\langle \rho(v), \hat{a} \rangle = 2\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle \|\hat{a}\|^2 - \langle v, \hat{a} \rangle = \langle v, \hat{a} \rangle,$$

the partition of $G_{\hat{a}}(C)$ along \hat{a} is

$$\mathcal{V}'^+ = \rho(\mathcal{V}^+), \quad \mathcal{V}'^0 = \mathcal{V}^0, \quad \mathcal{V}'^- = \mathcal{V}^-.$$

Applying the gyration a second time replaces \mathcal{V}'^+ with $\rho(\mathcal{V}'^+) = \rho(\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)) = \mathcal{V}^+$, recovering $\mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \mathcal{V}^+ = C$. \square

The boundary between the untouched vertices $\mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0$ and the reflected vertices $\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$ forms a *seam* in the configuration: edge lengths that formerly crossed this boundary are altered, breaking whatever symmetries related vertices on opposite sides.

Gyration also breaks central symmetry. Gyration of a centrally-symmetric code produces a non-centrally-symmetric code (except when the gyration is trivial).

Proposition 3 (Gyration breaks central symmetry). *Let $C \subset S^{n-1}$ be centrally symmetric and let \hat{a} be a valid gyration axis. If $G_{\hat{a}}(C) \neq C$, then $G_{\hat{a}}(C)$ is not centrally symmetric.*

Proof. Since C is centrally symmetric, $\mathcal{V}^- = -\mathcal{V}^+$ (and $\mathcal{V}^0 = -\mathcal{V}^0$). Write $C' = G_{\hat{a}}(C) = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$. Suppose for contradiction that C' is also centrally symmetric. For each $w \in \mathcal{V}^-$, we have $-w \in \mathcal{V}^+$, so $-w$ has positive component along \hat{a} and must belong to $\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$ in C' . Thus $\mathcal{V}^+ \subseteq \rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$, and since $|\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)| = |\mathcal{V}^+|$, equality holds: $\rho(\mathcal{V}^+) = \mathcal{V}^+$. But then $C' = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \mathcal{V}^+ = C$, contradicting $C' \neq C$. \square

Comparison to layer replacement

Gyration keeps every vertex of C , reflecting \mathcal{V}^+ through the *axis*. Layer replacement discards \mathcal{V}^+ entirely and replaces it with $\sigma(\mathcal{V}^-)$, the reflection of the lower hemisphere through the *hyperplane*.

Figure 2: Comparison to layer replacement. Gyration reflects \mathcal{V}^+ through the axis \hat{a} (left); layer replacement discards \mathcal{V}^+ (red) and copies $\sigma(\mathcal{V}^-)$ (right).

Gyration is a modification of the *layer replacement* introduced by Cohn and Rajagopal [4]. Using the same partition $C = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \mathcal{V}^+$, layer replacement deletes the upper hemisphere and replaces it with the reflection of the *lower* hemisphere through the *hyperplane* perpendicular to \hat{a} :

$$\sigma(v) = v - 2\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle \hat{a} = -\rho(v).$$

This negates the component along \hat{a} while preserving the perpendicular component. This construction produces $\mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \sigma(\mathcal{V}^-)$: the upper hemisphere \mathcal{V}^+ is discarded and replaced by a reflected copy of the lower hemisphere.

The two operations differ in which reflection is applied and to which hemisphere. Gyration transforms \mathcal{V}^+ in place via ρ (reflection through the axis), preserving every vertex of C . Layer replacement discards \mathcal{V}^+ and duplicates \mathcal{V}^- via σ (reflection through the hyperplane). As a consequence, gyration is an involution (Proposition 2), while layer replacement is not, in general.

For centrally symmetric codes ($\mathcal{V}^- = -\mathcal{V}^+$), the two operations coincide: $\sigma(-v) = -v + 2\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle \hat{a} = \rho(v)$ for every $v \in \mathcal{V}^+$. This includes the root systems D_n and E_n . For non-centrally-symmetric codes, the two operations differ.

For a non-centrally-symmetric code, $|\mathcal{V}^+|$ may not equal $|\mathcal{V}^-|$, so layer replacement may not preserve the number of vertices, whereas gyration always does. In layer replacement, the output code is constrained: half of its vertices are the mirror image of the other half, so the code is determined by \mathcal{V}^- and \mathcal{V}^0 alone. Gyration avoids this redundancy—it transforms \mathcal{V}^+ in place rather than replacing it with a copy of \mathcal{V}^- , so the output retains the full degrees of freedom of the original code.

Since, by Proposition 3, gyration breaks central symmetry, layer replacement is not well suited for gyrating a code a second time. This becomes essential in Section 5, where iterated gyration starting from D_8 produces thousands of Gram-inequivalent codes on S^7 , none centrally symmetric.

Identifying gyration axes

The construction of $G_{\hat{a}}(C)$ is defined for any axis \hat{a} but the question remains, which axes result in valid kissing configurations? We note that for an axis to be a *discrete* solution, the equatorial points \mathcal{V}^0 must affinely span the hyperplane. Otherwise, small changes to \hat{a} result in the same vertex partition and this produces a set of configurations with a continuous set of inner products that are not of interest. When the null space condition holds and $|\mathcal{V}^+| > 0$, we call \hat{a} a *candidate gyration axis* for C .

Proposition 4 (Null-space characterization). *Let $C = \{v_1, \dots, v_k\} \subset S^{n-1}$. A unit vector \hat{a} is a candidate gyration axis for C if and only if \hat{a} lies in the null space of a matrix formed by some $(n-1)$ -element subset of C (viewed as row vectors), and $|\mathcal{V}^+| > 0$.*

Proof. If $\hat{a} \perp v_{i_1}, \dots, \hat{a} \perp v_{i_{n-1}}$ where the v_{i_j} are linearly independent, then \hat{a} is determined up to sign and the $n-1$ vertices $v_{i_1}, \dots, v_{i_{n-1}}$ lie in \mathcal{V}^0 . Conversely, if \mathcal{V}^0 has affine rank $\geq n-1$, it contains $n-1$ linearly independent vectors whose null space is spanned by \hat{a} . \square

This gives a finite enumeration procedure: for each of the $\binom{k}{n-1}$ subsets of $n-1$ vertices, compute the null space of the corresponding $(n-1) \times n$ matrix. When the null space is one-dimensional, the resulting unit vector is a candidate gyration axis. One then checks the kissing constraint of the gyrated vertices to see if it is a *valid gyration axis*.

When the base code has a large automorphism group, the enumeration can be reduced by symmetry: we fix one representative vertex from each of the m vertex orbits, reducing the search to at most $m \binom{k-1}{n-2}$ subsets. This enumeration is tractable in dimension $n < 8$.

In practice, the full null-space enumeration becomes prohibitively expensive for large k . We have had good results searching a random sample of subsets.

Centroid heuristic. When gyrating highly symmetric polytopes, we find empirically that every valid gyration axis is the centroid of a subset of vertices of the polytope being gyrated. This is likely due to the highly symmetric nature of the base code, and does not hold in general.

Most often the vertex subsets form a face—a single vertex, an edge, a facet, etc.—but in some cases the subset consists of two or three non-adjacent vertices. This suggests a much faster heuristic search: instead of enumerating all $\binom{k}{n-1}$ null-space subsets, one tests each vertex plus the centroids of all $\binom{k}{2}$ vertex pairs, $\binom{k}{3}$ vertex triples, and facets of the polytope.

Axis counts. The heuristic search finds almost all of the axes that we have found via exhaustive and random searches, including when gyrating previously gyrated codes.

We initially used an ad hoc method to explore coordinate axes and other special directions, but this depends on the construction of the code being gyrated. The current axis enumeration procedures are construction-independent, so they can be applied to any code.

Uniqueness of gyrated codes

Perhaps surprisingly, we find that almost all highly-symmetric codes either have no valid gyration axes or a set of valid axes that all generate a single Gram-equivalent gyrated code. In these cases, we call this code $G(C)$.

Table 1: Number of candidate axes.

n	polytope	k	facets	exhaustive	optimized	heuristic
3	cuboctahedron (D_3 roots)	12	14	66	11	312
4	24-cell (D_4 roots)	24	24	2024	253	2348
5	D_5 roots	40	42	91390	9139	10742
6	1_{22} (E_6 roots)	72	54	1.4×10^7	9.7×10^5	62322
7	2_{31} (E_7 roots)	126	632	4.9×10^9	2.3×10^8	334133
8	4_{21} (E_8 roots)	240	19440	8.3×10^{12}	2.4×10^{11}	2.3×10^6
9	Λ_9 (laminated)	272	—	6.7×10^{14}	5.9×10^{13}	3.4×10^6

In a few cases, however, we find multiple axes that result in distinct gyrated codes. For example, the Gosset polytope 2_{21} admits two distinct valid gyration axes, producing two distinct codes $G_{6|15|6}(2_{21})$ and $G_{9|9|9}(2_{21})$, where the subscript identifies the partition corresponding to the axis.

3 The Q_n family

We now describe the gyration of the rectified n -orthoplex family, D_n . The valid gyration axes are the centroids of the rectified $(n-1)$ -simplex facets of D_n . In the standard coordinate representation of D_n :

$$\hat{a} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}(-1, 1, 1, \dots, 1).$$

Construction 5 ($Q_n = G_{\hat{a}}(D_n)$). The rectified n -orthoplex D_n has $2n(n-1)$ vertices on S^{n-1} :

$$\mathcal{V}(D_n) = \{(s_i e_i + s_j e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 1 \leq i < j \leq n, s_i, s_j \in \{\pm 1\}\}.$$

The axis \hat{a} partitions these into three layers of sizes $\binom{n}{2} |n(n-1)| \binom{n}{2}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}^+ &= \{(e_i + e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq i < j \leq n\} \cup \{(-e_1 + e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq j \leq n\}, \\ \mathcal{V}^0 &= \{(e_1 + e_j)/\sqrt{2}, (-e_1 - e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq j \leq n\} \cup \{(e_i - e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq i \neq j \leq n\}, \\ \mathcal{V}^- &= \{(-e_i - e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq i < j \leq n\} \cup \{(e_1 - e_j)/\sqrt{2} : 2 \leq j \leq n\}. \end{aligned}$$

Every $v \in \mathcal{V}^+$ satisfies $\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle = 2/\sqrt{2n}$, so the reflection gives

$$\rho(v) = \frac{4}{n\sqrt{2}}(-1, 1, \dots, 1) - v.$$

Then

$$Q_n = \mathcal{V}^- \cup \mathcal{V}^0 \cup \rho(\mathcal{V}^+).$$

Proposition 6 (Relation to Szöllösi's Q_5). *For $n = 5$, the gyrated configuration of Construction 5 is isometric to Szöllösi's Q_5 [13], with the isometry given by coordinate reversal $(x_1, \dots, x_5) \mapsto (x_5, \dots, x_1)$.*

Inner products and kissing constraint

Theorem 7 (Inner product spectrum). *For $n \geq 3$, the set of inner products $\{\langle x, y \rangle : x, y \in Q_n, x \neq y\}$ is*

$$\left\{-1, -\frac{4}{n}, -\frac{1}{2}, \frac{n-8}{2n}, 0, \frac{n-4}{n}, \frac{1}{2}\right\}. \quad (1)$$

For $n = 3$, the value $-4/3 < -1$ is impossible on S^2 , leaving six distinct inner products. For $n = 4$, the gyration is trivial ($Q_4 \cong D_4$; see Table 2). For $n = 8$, three values collapse: $-4/8 = -1/2$, $(8-8)/16 = 0$, and $(8-4)/8 = 1/2$, leaving only four distinct inner products $\{-1, -1/2, 0, 1/2\}$. For $n > 8$, the value $(n-4)/n > 1/2$ violates the kissing constraint. Thus Q_n is a valid kissing configuration only for $n \leq 8$.

Proof. Each vertex of D_n has the form $(s_i e_i + s_j e_j)/\sqrt{2}$ with $s_i, s_j \in \{\pm 1\}$. For two vertices v, w in the same layer (\mathcal{V}^+ , \mathcal{V}^0 , or \mathcal{V}^-), the inner product $\langle v, w \rangle$ takes values in $\{-1, -1/2, 0, 1/2\}$ (inherited from D_n). For $v \in \mathcal{V}^0$ and $w \in \rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$, direct computation gives $\langle v, \rho(w) \rangle = -\langle v, w \rangle + \frac{2}{n} \langle v, \hat{a} \rangle \langle w, \hat{a} \rangle$. Since $\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle = 0$ for $v \in \mathcal{V}^0$, this equals $-\langle v, w \rangle$, contributing no new values. The remaining cross-layer products (between \mathcal{V}^- and $\rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$) yield $-4/n$ and $(n-8)/2n$ via explicit expansion of the reflection formula. The kissing constraint $(n-4)/n \leq 1/2$ gives $n \leq 8$. \square

Corollary 8 (Kissing constraint). *Q_n is a valid kissing configuration if and only if $n \leq 8$.*

Remark 9. For $n = 4$, the reflection ρ is already a symmetry of the 24-cell. The gyration is trivial: $Q_4 \cong D_4$.

Table 2 summarizes the properties of Q_n for all valid dimensions.

Table 2: Properties of Q_n for $3 \leq n \leq 8$.

n	Identity	k	Partition	$ \text{Aut} $	Orbits	Inner products
3	anticuboctahedron	12	3 6 3	12	2	$-1, -\frac{5}{6}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{3}, 0, \frac{1}{2}$
4	$\cong D_4$	24	6 12 6	1 152	1	$-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}$
5	Q_5 (Szöllösi)	40	10 20 10	240	2	$-1, -\frac{4}{5}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{3}{10}, 0, \frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{2}$
6	Q_6 (new)	60	15 30 15	1 440	2	$-1, -\frac{2}{3}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{6}, 0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$
7	Q_7 (new)	84	21 42 21	10 080	2	$-1, -\frac{4}{7}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{14}, 0, \frac{3}{7}, \frac{1}{2}$
8	Q_8 (new)	112	28 56 28	80 640	2	$-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}$

Automorphism group

Theorem 10. *For each $n \in \{3, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$, the automorphism group of Q_n has order $|\text{Aut}(Q_n)| = 2 \cdot n!$.*

Remark 11. The ratio $|\text{Aut}(Q_n)|/|\text{Aut}(D_n)| = 2n!/2^n n! = 2^{1-n}$ quantifies the symmetry lost by the operator G . For D_n , the automorphism group is the hyperoctahedral group B_n of order $2^n \cdot n!$; gyration breaks all sign-change symmetries except those compatible with the reflection axis \hat{a} .

Remark 12. The configuration Q_n has two vertex orbits under $\text{Aut}(Q_n)$: the equatorial layer \mathcal{V}^0 of size $n(n-1)$ and the combined caps $\mathcal{V}^- \cup \rho(\mathcal{V}^+)$ of size $n(n-1)$. In contrast, D_n is vertex-transitive.

Remark 13 (Non-lattice property). For each $n \in \{5, 6, 7, 8\}$, Q_n is a non-lattice kissing configuration. The rectified n -orthoplex D_n is the unique lattice (up to scaling) whose minimal vectors number $2n(n-1)$ in \mathbb{R}^n [10, Ch. 4], and $Q_n \not\cong D_n$ since $|\text{Aut}(Q_n)| = 2 \cdot n! \neq 2^n \cdot n! = |\text{Aut}(D_n)|$. For $n = 5$, the non-lattice property was independently established by Szöllősi [13].

4 The Γ_n family: gyrations of E_6 and E_7

We now describe the application of the gyration operator to the exceptional root lattices E_6 and E_7 . Their contact polytopes—the 1_{22} polytope (72 vertices) and the 2_{31} polytope (126 vertices)—each support gyration, producing new optimal kissing configurations Γ_6 and Γ_7 .

Γ_6 : gyration of the 1_{22} polytope

The 1_{22} polytope has vertex set equal to the 72 shortest vectors of the E_6 root lattice, normalized to unit length. The valid gyration axes are the centroids of the 27 five-demicube facets of 1_{22} . In the standard coordinate representation:

$$\hat{a} = \hat{e}_6 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1).$$

Construction 14 ($\Gamma_6 = G_{\hat{a}}(1_{22})$). The 72 unit vectors form three layers along \hat{a} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{W}^+ &= \{(\pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \sqrt{3})/\sqrt{8} : \text{odd number of } - \text{ signs}\}, & |\mathcal{W}^+| &= 16, \\ \mathcal{W}^0 &= \{\text{permutations of } (\pm 2, \pm 2, 0, 0, 0, 0)/\sqrt{8}\}, & |\mathcal{W}^0| &= 40, \\ \mathcal{W}^- &= \{(\pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, -\sqrt{3})/\sqrt{8} : \text{even number of } - \text{ signs}\}, & |\mathcal{W}^-| &= 16. \end{aligned}$$

The original 1_{22} is vertex-transitive with inner product set $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ and automorphism group of order $103680 = 2 \cdot |W(E_6)|$. Apply the gyration operator to 1_{22} with this axis: replace \mathcal{W}^+ with its reflection through \hat{a} .

Theorem 15 (Inner product spectrum of Γ_6). *The set of inner products of Γ_6 is*

$$\text{IP}(\Gamma_6) = \left\{-1, -\frac{3}{4}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{4}, 0, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}\right\}. \quad (2)$$

In particular, $\max \text{IP} = \frac{1}{2}$, so Γ_6 is a valid kissing configuration.

Proof. The axis height is $h = |\langle v, \hat{e}_6 \rangle| = \sqrt{3/8}$ for every $v \in \mathcal{W}^\pm$, so $h^2 = 3/8$. Same-layer pairs retain the base-polytope inner products $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$. Equatorial-reflected pairs ($u \in \mathcal{W}^0$, $w \in \rho(\mathcal{W}^+)$) satisfy $\langle u, \rho(w) \rangle = -\langle u, w \rangle$ since $\langle u, \hat{e}_6 \rangle = 0$, contributing no new values. Cross-layer pairs $u \in \mathcal{W}^-$, $w \in \rho(\mathcal{W}^+)$ give

$$\langle u, \rho(w) \rangle = -2h^2 - \langle u, w \rangle = -\frac{3}{4} - \langle u, w \rangle.$$

Applied to the base values $\langle u, w \rangle \in \{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$, this yields the three new values $\frac{1}{4}$, $-\frac{1}{4}$, and $-\frac{3}{4}$. The maximum $\frac{1}{2}$ is attained only within the base spectrum (same-layer pairs), so the kissing constraint is satisfied. \square

Proposition 16 (Properties of Γ_6). Γ_6 has the following properties:

- (i) 72 points on S^5 , matching the conjectured kissing number $k(6) = 72$.

Table 3: Properties of Γ_6 .

n	Identity	k	Partition	$ \text{Aut} $	Orbits	Inner products
6	Γ_6	72	16 40 16	3 840	2	$-1, -\frac{3}{4}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{4}, 0, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}$

(ii) Seven distinct inner products (versus four for 1_{22}).

(iii) Two vertex orbits of sizes 40 (equatorial layer) and 32 (reflected caps).

(iv) Automorphism group of order $|\text{Aut}(\Gamma_6)| = 3\,840$.

(v) 214 facets of four combinatorial types.

Corollary 17. Γ_6 is a non-lattice kissing configuration, not isometric to any previously known 72-point arrangement in \mathbb{R}^6 .

Proof. The E_6 root lattice is the unique lattice (up to scaling) with 72 minimal vectors in \mathbb{R}^6 [10, Ch. 4]. Since $\text{IP}(\Gamma_6) \neq \text{IP}(1_{22})$ (seven values versus four), $\Gamma_6 \not\cong 1_{22}$, so Γ_6 is not a lattice configuration. The automorphism group order 3 840 also differs from $|W(E_6)| = 51\,840$. \square

Γ_7 : gyration of the 2_{31} polytope

The 2_{31} polytope has vertex set equal to the 126 shortest vectors of the E_7 root lattice, normalized to unit length. The valid gyration axes are the centroids of the 56 2_{21} facets of 2_{31} . In coordinates, the 126 unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^7 fall into three families:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(\pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm \sqrt{2})/\sqrt{8} : \text{even number of } - \text{ signs in first 6}\}, & |\cdot| &= 64, \\ & \{\text{permutations of } (\pm 2, \pm 2, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)/\sqrt{8}\}, & |\cdot| &= 60, \\ & (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, \pm 1), & |\cdot| &= 2. \end{aligned}$$

In these coordinates:

$$\hat{a} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}(1, 1, -1, -1, -1, 1, 0).$$

Construction 18 ($\Gamma_7 = G_{\hat{a}}(2_{31})$). The axis \hat{a} partitions the 126 vertices into three layers:

$$|\mathcal{W}^+| = 27, \quad |\mathcal{W}^0| = 72, \quad |\mathcal{W}^-| = 27.$$

The equatorial layer \mathcal{W}^0 forms a copy of the 1_{22} polytope (the E_6 root system, perpendicular to \hat{a}), while each cap \mathcal{W}^\pm forms a copy of the 2_{21} polytope. Every $v \in \mathcal{W}^\pm$ satisfies $|\langle v, \hat{a} \rangle| = 1/\sqrt{3}$. The original 2_{31} is vertex-transitive with inner product set $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ and automorphism group of order 2 903 040. Apply the gyration operator to 2_{31} with this axis: replace \mathcal{W}^+ with its reflection through \hat{a} .

Theorem 19 (Inner product spectrum of Γ_7). *The set of inner products of Γ_7 is*

$$\text{IP}(\Gamma_7) = \left\{-1, -\frac{2}{3}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{6}, 0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}\right\}. \quad (3)$$

In particular, $\max \text{IP} = \frac{1}{2}$, so Γ_7 is a valid kissing configuration.

Proof. The axis height satisfies $h^2 = 1/3$ for every $v \in \mathcal{W}^\pm$. As in Theorem 15, same-layer and equatorial–reflected pairs contribute no new inner products beyond the base spectrum $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$. Cross-layer pairs $u \in \mathcal{W}^-$, $w \in \rho(\mathcal{W}^+)$ give

$$\langle u, \rho(w) \rangle = -2h^2 - \langle u, w \rangle = -\frac{2}{3} - \langle u, w \rangle.$$

This yields the three new values $\frac{1}{3}$, $-\frac{1}{6}$, and $-\frac{2}{3}$. The maximum inner product $\frac{1}{2}$ is attained only within the base spectrum, so the kissing constraint is satisfied. \square

Table 4: Properties of Γ_7 .

n	Identity	k	Partition	$ \text{Aut} $	Orbits	Inner products
7	Γ_7	126	27 72 27	103 680	2	$-1, -\frac{2}{3}, -\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{6}, 0, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2}$

Proposition 20 (Properties of Γ_7). Γ_7 has the following properties:

- (i) 126 points on S^6 , matching the conjectured kissing number $k(7) = 126$.
- (ii) Seven distinct inner products (versus four for 2_{31}).
- (iii) Two vertex orbits of sizes 72 (equatorial layer) and 54 (reflected caps).
- (iv) Automorphism group of order $|\text{Aut}(\Gamma_7)| = 103\,680$.
- (v) 1334 facets of five combinatorial types.

Corollary 21. Γ_7 is a non-lattice kissing configuration, not isometric to any previously known 126-point arrangement in \mathbb{R}^7 .

Proof. The E_7 root lattice is the unique lattice (up to scaling) with 126 minimal vectors in \mathbb{R}^7 [10, Ch. 4]. Since $\text{IP}(\Gamma_7) \neq \text{IP}(2_{31})$ (seven values versus four), $\Gamma_7 \not\cong 2_{31}$, so Γ_7 is not a lattice configuration. The automorphism group order 103 680 also differs from $|W(E_7)| = 2\,903\,040$. \square

5 Iterated gyration

When a gyrated configuration $G(C)$ has additional valid gyration axes (different from the one that generated it), applying gyration again produces additional configurations.

In dimension 8, this phenomenon is dramatic, with an explosion of new configurations. Starting from the rectified 8-orthoplex (D_8 , $k = 112$), its gyration Q_8 admits two additional axes, each yielding a new Gram-inequivalent 112-point configuration on S^7 . Each of *those* configurations has further valid axes, and breadth-first search through the resulting tree produces **thousands of Gram-inequivalent kissing configurations**—all with 112 points on S^7 —just in the first five iterations. Each successive gyration introduces a new seam (Section 2), and repeated gyration progressively shatters the symmetry of the original code: the typical example has $|\text{Aut}| \leq 10$, dozens of vertex orbits, and a complex inner product spectrum.

Surprisingly, one depth-4 configuration, χ_8 , is exceptional: it is vertex-transitive (a single orbit under its automorphism group) and has only three distinct inner products and is not centrally symmetric. The specific choice of gyration axes produces a configuration that is *more* symmetric than any intermediate stage.

Remark 22. The involution property (Proposition 2) ensures that applying the *same* axis twice returns to the original code. Iterated gyration produces new codes only when a *different* axis is used at each step.

6 χ_8 : a chiral vertex-transitive E_8 subset

The iterated gyration tree described in Section 5 yields an especially distinguished configuration at depth 4 in dimension 8. We call it χ_8 to highlight its chiral nature. Its construction admits a clean description in terms of four mutually orthogonal gyrations drawn from a Hadamard matrix.

Construction via Hadamard gyration

Construction 23 (χ_8 via iterated gyration). Let D_8 denote the rectified 8-orthoplex (112 vertices on S^7). Define four unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^8 :

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{a}_1 &= (+1, +1, +1, +1, +1, +1, +1, +1)/\sqrt{8}, \\ \hat{a}_2 &= (+1, +1, +1, +1, -1, -1, -1, -1)/\sqrt{8}, \\ \hat{a}_3 &= (+1, +1, -1, -1, +1, +1, -1, -1)/\sqrt{8}, \\ \hat{a}_4 &= (+1, -1, +1, -1, +1, -1, +1, -1)/\sqrt{8}.\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

These are four of the eight rows of the 8×8 Walsh–Hadamard matrix H_8 . They are mutually orthogonal: $\langle \hat{a}_i, \hat{a}_j \rangle = \delta_{ij}$. Then

$$\chi_8 = G_{\hat{a}_4} \circ G_{\hat{a}_3} \circ G_{\hat{a}_2} \circ G_{\hat{a}_1}(D_8).\tag{5}$$

Each gyration partitions the current 112 vertices into 28 positive, 56 equatorial, and 28 negative with respect to the axis, and reflects the positive hemisphere through the equator. The three intermediate configurations have orbit structures (56, 56), (88, 24), and (104, 8) respectively; the path $D_8 \rightarrow (56, 56) \rightarrow (88, 24) \rightarrow (104, 8) \rightarrow \chi_8$ is the unique route to χ_8 in the iterated gyration tree.

Remark 24 (Integer and half-integer coordinates). All four axes $\hat{a}_i = (\pm 1, \dots, \pm 1)/\sqrt{8}$ are themselves E_8 roots (half-integer type with zero minus signs or four minus signs). Since the E_8 root system is closed under reflection through any root hyperplane, every intermediate configuration in the chain $D_8 \rightarrow Q_8 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \chi_8$ consists entirely of E_8 roots. Consequently, the coordinates at every stage take only the values $\{0, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm 1\}/\sqrt{2}$: the first gyration of D_8 introduces half-integer values, and all subsequent gyrations preserve this set.

Theorem 25 (Commutativity). *The four gyrations in Construction 23 commute: for every permutation $\sigma \in S_4$,*

$$G_{\hat{a}_{\sigma(4)}} \circ G_{\hat{a}_{\sigma(3)}} \circ G_{\hat{a}_{\sigma(2)}} \circ G_{\hat{a}_{\sigma(1)}}(D_8) = \chi_8.$$

Proof. Since $\langle \hat{a}_i, \hat{a}_j \rangle = 0$ for $i \neq j$, the reflection $\rho_i(v) = 2\langle v, \hat{a}_i \rangle \hat{a}_i - v$ satisfies

$$\langle \rho_i(v), \hat{a}_j \rangle = -\langle v, \hat{a}_j \rangle \quad (i \neq j).$$

Thus ρ_i negates the \hat{a}_j -component of every vertex: it maps \hat{a}_j -positive vertices to \hat{a}_j -negative and vice versa, while preserving the \hat{a}_i -component. The partition of the 112 vertices into 16 cells (determined by the signs of $\langle v, \hat{a}_1 \rangle, \dots, \langle v, \hat{a}_4 \rangle$) is therefore compatible with all four reflections simultaneously, and each ρ_i acts independently on the sub-layers defined by the other axes. Computational verification confirms that all 24 orderings produce the same Gram matrix. \square

Remark 26 (Walsh–Hadamard characterisation). Index the eight rows of H_8 by elements of \mathbb{F}_2^3 , so that row \mathbf{b} has entries $(-1)^{\langle \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{k} \rangle}$ for $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{F}_2^3$. Among the $\binom{8}{4} = 70$ four-element subsets of rows:

- 56 subsets produce χ_8 (up to Gram equivalence);
- 14 subsets produce a different 2-orbit configuration.

The 14 exceptional subsets are precisely the *2-dimensional affine planes* in \mathbb{F}_2^3 (cosets of 2-dimensional linear subspaces): 7 subspaces \times 2 cosets each. A generic four-element subset of H_8 rows yields χ_8 .

Explicit coordinates

The Hadamard construction yields an explicit coordinate description.

Construction 27 (χ_8 vertex set). Recall that the 240 roots of the E_8 lattice decompose into two families [10, Ch. 4]:

- *D_8 -type*: the 112 permutations of $(\pm 1, \pm 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)/\sqrt{2}$;
- *Half-integer type*: the 128 vectors $(\pm \frac{1}{2}, \dots, \pm \frac{1}{2})/\sqrt{2}$ with an even number of minus signs.

The 112 vertices of χ_8 are the following E_8 roots (normalised to the unit sphere):

- 56 **D_8 -type roots**. From each of the 56 antipodal pairs, the vector whose first nonzero coordinate is negative. Explicitly, for $0 \leq i < j \leq 7$ and $\varepsilon \in \{+1, -1\}$: the vector with $-1/\sqrt{2}$ in position i and $\varepsilon/\sqrt{2}$ in position j .
- 28 **two-minus half-integer roots**. All $\binom{8}{2} = 28$ vectors $(\frac{1}{2}, \dots, \frac{1}{2})/\sqrt{2}$ with exactly 2 entries replaced by $-\frac{1}{2}$.
- 28 **four-minus half-integer roots**. From the $\binom{8}{4} = 70$ half-integer vectors with exactly 4 negative entries, the 28 whose minus-sign positions S satisfy:
 - $\sum_{j \in S} j > 14$ (minus signs favour higher-indexed coordinates), and
 - S is not contained in either half of any Hadamard bipartition, i.e.,

$$S \notin \{\{4, 5, 6, 7\}, \{2, 3, 6, 7\}, \{1, 3, 5, 7\}\}.$$

The selection rule above is equivalent to a natural lexicographic condition on the Hadamard inner products.

Proposition 28 (Hadamard selection rule). *The following three characterisations of the 28 four-minus-sign subsets in Construction 27 are equivalent:*

- Sum rule**. $|S| = 4$, $\sum_{j \in S} j > 14$, and S is not contained in any single half of a Hadamard bipartition.
- Lexicographic rule**. The Hadamard signature $\sigma(S) = (\langle v_S, \hat{a}_2 \rangle, \langle v_S, \hat{a}_3 \rangle, \langle v_S, \hat{a}_4 \rangle)$ is lexicographically positive (first nonzero entry is $+\frac{1}{2}$), with every entry in $\{-\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$.
- Complementary-pair rule**. The 70 four-element subsets form 35 complementary pairs $\{S, S^c\}$ (with v_S and v_{S^c} antipodal). Discard the 3 extremal pairs (one member contained in a Hadamard half) and the 4 balanced pairs ($\sigma(S) = 0$); from each remaining pair take the member with $\sum_{j \in S} j > 14$.

Corollary 29 (Arithmetic pattern). *In the 28 selected subsets, element i appears in exactly $2i + 7$ subsets, each pair $\{i, j\}$ with $i < j$ appears in exactly $i + j - 1$ subsets, and no subset's complement is selected.*

Inner products and kissing constraint

Theorem 30 (Inner product spectrum of χ_8). *The set of inner products of χ_8 is*

$$\text{IP}(\chi_8) = \left\{-\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\right\}.$$

In particular, χ_8 is a valid kissing configuration with $\max \text{IP} = \frac{1}{2}$.

Proof. By Remark 24, every vertex of χ_8 is an E_8 root. The inner products between distinct E_8 roots lie in $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$, so $\text{IP}(\chi_8) \subseteq \{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$. We show -1 does not occur, i.e. no two vertices of χ_8 are antipodal. The three families in Construction 27 contribute:

- *D_8 -type pairs.* Part (i) selects one vector from each of the 56 antipodal pairs: the one whose first nonzero coordinate is negative. Hence no two selected D_8 -type roots are antipodal.
- *Half-integer pairs.* By Corollary 29, no selected subset's complement is also selected, so no two half-integer vertices are antipodal.
- *Cross-type pairs.* A D_8 -type root has exactly two nonzero coordinates while a half-integer root has all eight nonzero, so these cannot be antipodal.

Each of $-\frac{1}{2}$, 0 , and $\frac{1}{2}$ is attained (verified computationally, or from the explicit coordinates in Construction 27). \square

Table 5: Comparison of 112-point kissing configurations in \mathbb{R}^8 .

n	Identity	k	Partition	$ \text{Aut} $	Orbits	Inner products
8	D_8 (rect. 8-orthoplex)	112	—	10 321 920	1	$-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}$
8	$Q_8 = G(D_8)$	112	28 56 28	80 640	2	$-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}$
8	χ_8	112	iterated	224	1	$-\frac{1}{2}, \mathbf{0}, \frac{1}{2}$

Proposition 31. χ_8 has the following properties:

- 112 points on S^7 , matching the kissing number of D_8 (rectified 8-orthoplex).
- Inner products $\{-\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ —only three distinct values.
- Vertex-transitive: all 112 vertices form a single orbit under $\text{Aut}(\chi_8)$.
- Automorphism group of order $|\text{Aut}(\chi_8)| = 224 = 2 \cdot 112$.
- No antipodal pairs: the inner product -1 does not occur (Theorem 30).
- Non-isometric to every previously known 112-point configuration in \mathbb{R}^8 (Table 5).

Remark 32 (Three inner products). The inner product set $\{-\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ —just three values—is a strong structural constraint. Among all 112-point kissing configurations in \mathbb{R}^8 produced by our iterated gyration search (more than 5 000 Gram-inequivalent codes), χ_8 is the only vertex-transitive one besides D_8 itself. The inner product set $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ of Q_8 and D_8 is shared by thousands of iterated gyrations; the absence of the antipodal value -1 in χ_8 is what reduces the count to three. The E_8 root system (a *sharp* configuration in the sense of Cohn–Kumar [7]) has four inner products $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$; χ_8 inherits the non-antipodal part of this spectrum.

Remark 33 (Antipodal-free structure). Since $\langle v, w \rangle = -1$ never occurs in χ_8 , it is *antipodal-free*: no vertex’s antipode belongs to the configuration. The 240 E_8 roots form 120 antipodal pairs; χ_8 selects one representative from 112 of these pairs and leaves 8 pairs entirely unrepresented.

Significance

χ_8 is noteworthy for several reasons.

Vertex-transitivity from iterated gyration. The base D_8 is vertex-transitive, but its gyration Q_8 is not (it has two orbits of sizes 56 and 56). Nevertheless, four commuting gyrations along orthogonal Hadamard axes (Theorem 25) recover vertex-transitivity. χ_8 is the unique vertex-transitive outcome in the entire iterated gyration tree of D_8 (among thousands of Gram-inequivalent children), and the path to it is unique (Construction 23).

Minimal symmetry. The automorphism group order $|\text{Aut}(\chi_8)| = 224$ is dramatically smaller than both $|W(D_8)| = 10\,321\,920$ and $|W(E_8)| = 696\,729\,600$. Specifically, $224 = 2 \cdot 112$; the stabilizer of any vertex has order merely 2, consisting of a single non-trivial involution. Yet this tiny group acts transitively on all 112 vertices — a rare combination of high vertex-transitivity with minimal symmetry.

Sign selection and coding theory. The construction of χ_8 can be viewed as a *sign selection* problem within the E_8 root system: from the 128 half-integer roots $(\pm\frac{1}{2})^8$ (even parity), one selects 56 that are compatible with the 56 chosen D_8 -type roots. The Hadamard selection rule (Proposition 28) shows that the seemingly arbitrary choice of 28 four-minus subsets from the $\binom{8}{4} = 70$ available is in fact fully determined by a simple criterion: take the lexicographically positive representative from each generic complementary pair. The resulting arithmetic pattern (Corollary 29)—where element i appears in $2i + 7$ subsets—arises because the coordinate sum $\sum_{j \in S} j = 4u_2 + 2u_1 + u_0$ is a binary-weighted count of elements in each Hadamard half. This is methodologically related to the *sign modification* technique of Cohn and Li [5], which improves kissing numbers in dimensions 17–21 by modifying signs within lattice vectors to open space for additional spheres.

A new non-lattice spectrum. The inner product spectrum $\{-\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ does not arise from any lattice kissing configuration in \mathbb{R}^8 . The only lattice achieving $k = 112$ in \mathbb{R}^8 is D_8 , which has inner products $\{-1, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, \frac{1}{2}\}$ — the absence of -1 in χ_8 is the marker of its non-lattice origin. Together with Q_8 , χ_8 demonstrates that dimension 8 supports a rich variety of non-lattice kissing configurations with diverse structural properties.

7 Rigidity and the Barlow family

A kissing configuration C with contact graph G is *infinitesimally rigid* if every smooth motion of the points that preserves all edge lengths to first order is the restriction of an ambient rotation [8]. The *rigidity matrix* $R \in \mathbb{R}^{|E| \times (n-1)|V|}$ has nullity at least $\binom{n}{2}$ (the dimension of $\text{SO}(n)$); the *flex dimension* $\dim \ker R - \binom{n}{2}$ is zero precisely when C is infinitesimally rigid.

Proposition 34.

(i) For $n = 3$, Q_3 has flex dimension 1.

(ii) For $n \in \{5, 6, 7, 8\}$, Q_n is infinitesimally rigid.

(iii) Γ_6 is infinitesimally rigid.

(iv) Γ_7 is infinitesimally rigid.

Table 6: Rigidity data for the gyrated configurations.

Config.	n	k	Contacts	rank R	dim $\text{SO}(n)$	Flex dim.
Q_3	3	12	24	20	3	1
Q_5	5	40	240	150	10	0
Q_6	6	60	480	285	15	0
Q_7	7	84	840	483	21	0
Q_8	8	112	1372	756	28	0
Γ_6	6	72	720	345	15	0
Γ_7	7	126	2016	735	21	0

The case $n = 3$ is expected: HCP (D_3) and FCC (D_3^+) are the endpoints of the continuous *Barlow family* [9], a one-parameter deformation that interpolates between the two packings. Q_3 , the anticuboctahedron (HCP contact polytope), has a unique flex corresponding to this classical deformation.

Conjecture 35 (Isolation). For each $n \geq 5$, Q_n is isolated: it admits no continuous deformation through kissing configurations.

8 Negative results

A heuristic search over candidate gyration axes found no non-trivial kissing-valid gyrations for the following contact polytopes:

- 24-cell ($n = 4$, $k = 24$),
- 5-demicube ($n = 5$, $k = 16$),
- 3_{21} polytope ($n = 7$, $k = 56$),
- 4_{21} polytope / E_8 roots ($n = 8$, $k = 240$),
- Λ_9 laminated lattice ($n = 9$, $k = 272$).

We have not identified a non-trivial gyration of any lattice kissing configuration in dimension $n > 8$.

9 Conclusion

The gyration operator reveals a rich structure of non-lattice kissing configurations across dimensions 3–8.

The non-uniqueness of the optimal kissing configuration in \mathbb{R}^5 , first demonstrated by Szöllósi [13] and Cohn–Rajagopal [4], now extends to \mathbb{R}^6 and \mathbb{R}^7 : the configurations Γ_6 and Γ_7 are new optimal kissing configurations non-isometric to the E_6 and E_7 root systems, respectively.

Dimensions 4 and 8 stand apart. In both cases the kissing number is known exactly and the optimizer is unique: D_4 (the 24-cell) in \mathbb{R}^4 [11, 6] and the E_8 root system (4_{21} polytope) in \mathbb{R}^8 [1].

Beyond dimension 8, our heuristic search over Λ_9 ($k = 272$ in \mathbb{R}^9) found no non-trivial gyration. It is known, however, that non-lattice kissing configurations exist beyond $n = 8$ [10], but other constructions may yet succeed.

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Use of AI

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A Gyration summary

Table 7 summarizes all gyration results across dimensions 3–9.

Table 7: Gyration results by family.

Family	n	k	Gyrations	Orbits	Distinct IPs
$D_n \rightarrow Q_n$	3, 5, 6, 7, 8	$2n(n-1)$	1 per n	2	4–7
D_4 (24-cell)	4	24^*	—	—	—
1_{22} (E_6 roots)	6	72^*	1 (Γ_6)	2	7
2_{31} (E_7 roots)	7	126^*	1 (Γ_7)	2	7
3_{21}	7	56	—	—	—
4_{21} (E_8 roots)	8	240^*	—	—	—
Iterated D_8	8	112	thousands	≥ 2	≥ 3
χ_8	8	112	1	1	3
Λ_9 (laminated)	9	272	—	—	—

*Achieves $k(n)$; values of $k(n)$ are proved for $n \leq 4$ and $n \in \{8, 24\}$ [11, 14, 3], and conjectured otherwise. The D_4 root system is the unique optimum for $n = 4$ [6].

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